

Perceptions of using electric light vehicles in cities: Survey results from six cities in the ELVITEN project

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Abstract

This paper describes a large scale public travel and attitude survey focusing on six cities (three in Italy and one each in Spain, Greece and Germany), to ascertain attitudes and possible usage of electric light (L-category) vehicles as an alternative to conventional vehicles. It also includes data from interviews of fleet operators. This work forms the first main stage of the EU project ELVITEN that demonstrates usage schemes for these types of vehicles in the six pilot cities. The project's aim is to increase the use of electric two-, three- and light four-wheel vehicles in cities as an alternative to car and conventional powered light vehicles, as a compliment to public transport and as a mode for light urban deliveries, including last-mile distribution.

Keywords:

Public perception, Electromobility, Traveller behaviour

Introduction

L-category vehicles (L-Vs) comprise light passenger and goods vehicles, from power-assisted bicycles, scooters and motorcycles to three- and four-wheeled micro-cars and vans. In many European cities, especially in southern Europe, these vehicles are popular for personal transport and light goods use, due to their low cost, easy manoeuvrability in congested traffic situations and easier parking than cars or vans. However they typically have Internal Combustion Engines and create pollution and noise in the urban environment. The shift towards electromobility so far has largely focused on cars, public transport vehicles and light goods and municipal service vehicles. Apart from electric bicycles, the adoption of electric versions of L-category vehicles, known as EL-Vs, is relatively slow. The three-year EU project ELVITEN [1] seeks to realise the potential of EL-Vs by establishing usage schemes in six pilot cities and evaluating their impacts on driving and charging patterns, as well as the overall effects on transport networks and city liveability.

The ELVITEN project (Electrified L-category Vehicles Integrated into Transport and Electricity Networks) aims to create a mobility change in urban areas from Internal Combustion Engine vehicles

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(both cars and light vehicles) to EL-Vs, while integrating them with existing transport networks, for example use of an EL-V as part of a multimodal journey including public transport. The aim is to shift towards more sustainable travel, so EL-Vs should complement walking, cycling and public transport, not compete against them.

An early task in the project was to measure baseline user perceptions and attitudes in the project's six demonstration cities, which are Rome, Genoa, Bari, Malaga, Trikala and Berlin. This paper describes the key outcomes of this work.

Survey aims and approach

Potential users of EL-Vs in cities are members of the public (for uses such as commuting, shopping, visiting or leisure) and businesses which operate fleets of vehicles (for deliveries, renting out, or for use of their own internal staff). A different approach to data collection was used for each. The former relied on a user-friendly questionnaire that aimed to maximise the number of responses. The latter group focused on a limited number of fleet operators with qualitative interviews of managers and drivers to uncover their transport/mobility needs and perceptions of EL-Vs.

In both cases, the survey provided information for the next stages of the project on aspects such as:

- The key opportunities (which groups of people are most likely to switch to EL-V use);
- The user expectations;
- The barriers people and companies see to using EL-Vs and how they can be overcome;
- Which types of EL-V (size, other features such as a roof or luggage capacity) are most favoured by different groups of people in the different cities;
- The likely frequency of use;
- The attitudes to ownership or renting/sharing of EL-Vs.

Public questionnaire on citizen's perceptions: Development and dissemination

An online questionnaire was developed and targeted to members of the public, comprising 26 questions in an anonymous format. This included contextual (factual) questions such as frequency of current urban trip for different reasons (work or education, shopping, visiting or leisure), distance, main mode of transport used, as well as age group, gender and occupation status (employed, student, unemployed, retired, etc.). The remainder of the questionnaire asked about whether respondents would consider using different types of EL-V (two-, three- or four-wheelers) for these purposes, whether they would use an EL-V sharing scheme, whether or not they consider the various types of EL-V to be comfortable, safe, easy to park and to charge, cheap to run, and to have sufficient luggage capacity. Respondents were also asked whether would consider using an EL-V as a part of multi-modal journey, with for instance public transport, and what they think the most important measures are to encourage greater use of these kinds of vehicles.

The questionnaire was developed and tested using an online survey tool, including questionnaire skip logic so that users are not presented with questions that are irrelevant to them. It was designed to take

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around ten minutes to complete and had to be understandable by all citizens, regardless of their knowledge of EL-Vs, their travel behaviour or their city/country of residence. Most questions were multiple-choice in order to facilitate responses and to make the analysis easier (e.g. in Figure 1). However, a few questions required textual answers so a certain amount of manual analysis in different languages was required.

The survey was developed in English and translated into Italian, Spanish, Greek and German, the languages of the demonstration cities. It could be answered by any citizen (including in other cities/countries – the respondent’s city is asked in case it is not one of the six included in the project) and a user could respond in any language regardless of the city or country where he or she lives. Each language version had a link to the other four languages in order to give people a choice.

14. In the future, would you consider using one of the following vehicles? If your answer is no, please skip to the next question.

	 Electric four-wheel LIGHT vehicle (not an electric car)			
for trips to work/education	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
for trips for shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
for trips for leisure, entertainment and visits (family/friends) within my city	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 1 – Example of a multiple-choice question in the online public questionnaire (English version)

The questionnaire was made accessible by a simple URL: www.research.net/r/ELVITEN-xx, where xx is the language version (EN, IT, DE, GR or ES). This link was widely distributed on websites and social media by ELVITEN partners in the demonstration cities and beyond (e.g. Figure 2).

The online questionnaire survey ran for approximately six weeks, from late December 2017 to mid-February 2018 and the total number of questionnaires submitted by that date was 8240, with a completion rate of between 63% and 87%, depending on the country/language. It was decided that eligible questionnaires for analysis would be those that were answered at least up to the first subjective question (as opposed to factual questions) and were from one of the six demonstration cities or a nearby town (within reasonable commuting distance). Hence there were 6988 eligible responses in total (eligible responses by city were as follows: Malaga 734, Berlin 754, Bari 813, Trikala 928, Genoa 1145 and Rome 2614).

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Figure 2 – Example of questionnaire survey publicity on Twitter

Given the different numbers of responses from each of the six cities, in the analysis each city's responses are given in terms of percentage of all eligible respondents from each city.

As it was a freely open survey, without quotas, it should be noted that the sample of respondents might not be typical of all the cities' populations, as there may be a bias according to the media used to disseminate the questionnaire, e.g. because it was online and disseminated on certain websites only. This is a likely reason why there were relatively few respondents in the over 60 age group.

Interview survey of fleet operators: Development and execution

In parallel, interviews (either face-to-face or by telephone) were conducted with 37 fleet operators and 22 professional drivers across the six study cities (ranging from 6 to 14 interviews per city). As ELVITEN is not only oriented to personal transport using EL-Vs but also business use of these types of vehicles, the aim was to solicit the opinions of managers and drivers responsible for light goods distribution in the six demonstration cities, from small companies (for example pizza delivery by scooter) to large ones (such as the national postal service or global logistics companies). It also included companies that rent out or share vehicles to the public (not just L-Vs but all types from pedal cycles to cars), to gain their views as to whether adding EL-Vs to their rental fleet would be an attractive proposition and, if so, under what circumstances.

Separate questionnaires were developed for fleet managers and fleet drivers. The former focused on the nature of the current vehicle fleet and the types of operations it undertakes (size and nature of load, distances driven, whether mostly urban deliveries or long distance, etc.) and perceptions of the suitability of EL-Vs to carry out some or all of these operations, as well as their advantages and barriers to their use. The latter focused on the driver's task and needs, asking perceptions of different types of EL-Vs with respect to comfort, safety, manoeuvrability, parking, etc., in a similar way to the public questionnaire survey.

The interviews were carried out by local partners in each city, in the national language, with responses

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then being grouped and analysed in an anonymous way (recording the kind of company and the city, but no personal information).

Because of the small sample size, these results are treated as qualitative only, i.e. giving a snapshot of attitudes and reasons behind them. Quantitative statistical analysis is not possible. For example, many operators were small businesses with fewer than ten vehicles, but one operator was a national postal service with thousands of vehicles nationwide, hence analysing such diverse operations together would produce skewed and essentially valueless results. The purpose was to look at the range of attitudes, needs and barriers, and not to produce statistical data.

Key results of public questionnaire

Current travel behaviour

As expected, actual use of EL-Vs is very low in all cities, but the five cities in southern Europe (in Italy, Spain and Greece) have a significant modal share of petrol L-Vs (scooters, motorcycles and three-wheelers). Berlin has a higher use of bicycles, public transport and electric cars but a lower proportion of users of petrol L-Vs. The high L-V use in the southern European cities indicates an opportunity to shift to electric versions of these vehicles, while in Berlin the greater familiarity with electro-mobility (cars) could also indicate greater potential for EL-Vs.

Willingness to use an EL-V sharing scheme

The first subjective question was “If there was a sharing scheme for these kinds of light electric vehicles in your local area would you consider using it?” (see results in Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Willingness to use an EL-V sharing scheme

There appeared to be a high level of interest in such schemes, with a majority of respondents in all cases except for Berlin saying they would use such a scheme either frequently or occasionally. In Berlin, these two categories nevertheless accounted for almost half of respondents, but with more people responding “maybe”. Berlin had the greatest proportion of respondents who would not consider using an EL-V at all, but even this proportion was only 16%. The levels of interest in Rome and Bari were particularly high.

Overall, there was relatively little difference in opinions between female and male respondents to this question, however in Bari women were more likely to be positive about using such schemes, whereas in Malaga, men appeared to be more inclined to use a sharing scheme.

Willingness to use EL-Vs for different travel purposes

The survey asked “in the future, would you consider using one of the following vehicles?” with a choice of bicycle (this option included electrically assisted bicycles) and 2-, 3- and 4-wheeled EL-Vs. For work or education trips, there seems to be more willingness among men than women to use both bicycles and most types of EL-Vs across all cities, especially with regard to bicycle use in the three Italian cities. Overall willingness to use a bicycle for work or education purposes is highest in Malaga, perhaps due to the relatively flat topography, the climate and the existence of a bike sharing scheme. 2 and 4-wheel EL-Vs were the most popular types in all cities except for Berlin, where 3-wheel EL-Vs were seen as attractive by the greatest number of respondents. The willingness to use bicycles and EL-Vs for shopping trips was noticeably lower than for commuting trips, quite understandably due to luggage carrying issues.

Perceptions of EL-V attributes

Regarding perceived comfort of EL-Vs, respondents stated that they would feel more comfortable in 4-wheel EL-Vs, and this is true for both men and women and for all age groups. More men stated that they would feel comfortable using all these types of vehicles than was the case for women (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Perceptions of Comfort of EL-Vs for all cities combined (split by gender)

In terms of age group, more people aged 30-59 stated that they would feel more comfortable than the other age groups using 2-wheelers or 3-wheelers (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Perceptions of Comfort of EL-Vs for all cities combined (split by age group)

No notable differences in comfort perceptions per city were observed.

Other perception attributes were analysed in a similar way. These were:

- **Ease of parking:** unsurprisingly, parking was seen as being easier for 2-wheeled EL-Vs than the other categories. There was little difference between women and men, while in terms of age; younger respondents considered parking to be easier than older respondents.
- **Safety:** Perceptions of EL-V safety increased with the vehicle size (number of wheels). Men were slightly more likely than woman to say that they would feel safe using one. Younger age groups would also feel safer than older ones, although the difference is less marked for 4-wheeled EL-Vs. Respondents from Rome and Bari had the greatest safety concerns (between 60 and 70% considered that they would not feel safe using 2-wheeled EL-Vs), while Berlin and Trikala respondents had fewer concerns (just over 50% would feel safe or fairly safe using one).
- **Convenience of charging EL-Vs:** Perceptions on this attribute hardly differed according to the type of EL-V. Men and younger respondents were slightly more likely than women or older age groups to consider them convenient to charge. Respondents in Bari and Rome considered charging to be more convenient than those in other cities (over 50% agreed it was convenient), including Berlin even though that city currently has the most comprehensive charging infrastructure of the six demonstration cities.
- **Affordability of operating EL-Vs:** between 40 and 80% considered EL-V use to be affordable. Men were slightly more likely than women to consider EL-Vs as being affordable, while there were no significant differences in this question by age group. 60 to 80% of respondents in Malaga and Bari considered EL-V operation to be affordable (differences according to vehicle

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type), whereas only 40 to 60% in Berlin considered them to be affordable.

- Luggage capacity of EL-Vs: Respondents agreeing that luggage capacity was sufficient for their needs increased with the number of wheels of the EL-V. Men and younger age groups were more likely to agree with this statement than women and older age groups, although differences among these were very slight. Overall, 24% considered that 2-wheeled EL-Vs had sufficient luggage capacity for their needs, with this rising to 34% for 2-wheeled EL-Vs and 67% for 4-wheelers.

Willingness to use EL-Vs as part of a multimodal journey

Respondents were asked “do you, or would you consider, using one of these kinds of electric vehicles as a part of multi-modal journey, with for instance public transport?” This was a multiple choice question with only one possible answer. Very few people use EL-Vs as part of multimodal journeys at present. A considerable majority (70 to 90%) in the three Italian cities and Malaga said they would consider using EL-Vs as part of a multimodal journey. Although this is only a stated preference study and does not commit people, the level of positive consideration is quite impressive. Even in Berlin, where enthusiasm appears to be more muted, 65% of respondents would consider using an EL-V in this way. According to gender, there was a slight propensity for men to be more likely to consider using EL-Vs as part of a multimodal journey than women, except in Trikala where the level of interest between men and women was almost the same.

Measures to encourage the use of EL-Vs

Respondents were asked “what in your opinion are the most necessary measures to encourage greater use of these kinds of electric vehicles?” with a list of suggested measures given. Sufficient electric charging infrastructure was the most popular measure in every city, but the second most popular measure varied, with incentive schemes taking second place in Bari and Trikala, sufficient secure parking in Berlin and Malaga, and allowing use of bus lanes by EL-Vs in Genoa and Rome.

Key results of operator (manager/driver) interviews

Advantages and Disadvantages of EVs

The manager interviewees were asked to indicate what in their opinions the main advantages (or motivations) and disadvantages (or barriers) of EVs/EL-Vs are. The interview data showed that the interviewees appreciate that EVs have a number of advantages including environmental friendliness, low costs for maintenance and use, the possibility to access limited traffic zones, flexibility in traffic, lower noise, and that they are an innovative solution.

On the other hand, concerns expressed by interviewees included battery autonomy and low driving distance (range), difficulty in electricity supply / charging, battery lifecycle and disposal of life-expired batteries, duration of charging times, and current limited range EV models.

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Attitudes towards partial fleet renewal using EL-Vs

Regarding attitudes towards EL-Vs, over 80% of fleet manager respondents would consider (or have already considered) changing at least some of their vehicle fleet from cars, vans or petrol L-Vs to EL-Vs.

Measures to Encourage Greater Use of EVs/EL-Vs

Four measures to encourage greater use of electric vehicles including EL-Vs were put to interviewees as follows:

Measure 1: Dedicated delivery spaces (on street)

- About 60% of the managers interviewed who answered this question said that this measure was either very or quite important.
- 11 managers believe that improvements to dedicated delivery spaces are needed whereas only 4 did not.
- Just over half of the drivers interviewed said that this measure was either very or quite important, and that improvements were needed in this area.

Measure 2: Electric charging infrastructure

- 28 of 30 (93%) managers interviewed who answered this question said that this measure was either very or quite important and only 2 said it wasn't.
- The majority of them believe that improvements to charging infrastructure are needed.
- Three quarters of drivers said that this measure was either very or quite important and most agreed that improvements to electric charging infrastructure are needed.

Measure 3: Allow use of bus and cycle lanes by 2- or 3-wheel electric vehicles, or other means of priority or safety measures on the roads

- Amongst 30 managers who answered this question, 14 of them believed that this measure was either very or quite important, but 16 said no.
- 18 managers said that improvements to this measure are needed whereas only 7 said no.
- Just over half of drivers said that this measure was either very or quite important and most of them believe that improvements to this measure are needed.

Measure 4: Specific navigation services aimed at electric light vehicles

- As with the previous measure, 30 managers answered this question with 14 believing that this measure was either very or quite important.
- 13 managers said that improvements to this measure are needed whereas only 5 said no.
- Again, just over half of drivers said that this measure was either very or quite important, with just half of them believing that improvements to this measure are needed.

Conclusions and implications

Bari, Rome, Genoa, Malaga, and Trikala all had a large observed interest in EL-V sharing schemes. Berlin and Trikala had the potential to increase their sharing scheme usage by attracting users that were still unsure. A higher percentage of respondents in Berlin would either prefer to buy their own or

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would not consider using them at all.

Across all cities, men were observed to be more inclined to use EL-Vs for trips related to work or education purposes than women. Cycling was a more popular choice than EL-Vs in all the cities for leisure and personal trips. Topography had some effect e.g. Genoa is very hilly and less suitable for cycling; Bari and Malaga are much flatter. Also in terms of modal choice, Berlin and Rome have the most comprehensive public transport and especially in Berlin this may be a reason for the lower than average enthusiasm for EL-Vs.

Sufficient electric charging infrastructure was noted as a major factor where improvements are needed in order to boost EV/EL-V use. Dedicated delivery spaces on streets were considered an important measure to fleet operators and drivers in order to encourage greater use of electric vehicles including EL-Vs.

Instead of owning EL-V vehicles, the majority of the respondents would prefer to use shared or rented vehicles, and were likely to consider using EL-Vs as part of a multimodal journey.

Among the fleet operators interviewed varied in both scale (from local to global), and type (from delivery businesses to sharing services). Despite this, very positive attitudes towards EL-Vs were observed.

In general, a higher percentage of women and elderly declared “Don’t know” across almost all the attributes. The ELVITEN schemes should therefore focus in particular on women and elderly populations as future target audiences for awareness and training activities to encourage knowledge of EL-Vs in citizens.

References

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